

TITLE:

“Enhancing Therapeutics Radiographers' autonomy in IGRT through structured training: a Protocol for a Quality improvement Project”

Authors:

Boriani M.¹, Maran I.^{2}, Assenza M.², Peghetti A.², Angelini G.¹, Gilli E.¹, Casarotti F.¹, Morganti A.G.¹, Strigari L.³, Durante S.^{2,4}*

¹Radiation Oncology, IRCCS Azienda Ospedaliero-Universitaria di Bologna, Italy

²Professional development and implementation of research in health professions unit, IRCCS Azienda Ospedaliero-Universitaria di Bologna, Italy

³Department of Medical Physics, IRCCS Azienda Ospedaliero-Universitaria di Bologna, Italy

⁴Department of Healthcare Professions, IRCCS Azienda Ospedaliero-Universitaria di Bologna, Italy

**Corresponding author*

ABSTRACT**(Aim**

This initiative is distinguished by its multidimensional approach, encompassing clinical, educational, and organizational outcomes. It aims to provide reproducible evidence to support RTT role expansion and to contribute toward the definition of national standards for IGRT training and practice.)

Background

IGRT has become an essential component in delivering precise and effective radiotherapy treatment. However, in many healthcare institutions, the responsibility for online image matching remains within the exclusive domain of Radiation Oncologists (ROs). This can result in workflow inefficiencies and delays in patient treatment. In light of increasing technological capabilities and evolving professional roles, there is growing interest in expanding the scope of Therapeutic Radiographers (RTTs) to take on more autonomous responsibilities within the IGRT process.

This study introduces a structured, reproducible protocol combining educational content, objective performance metrics, and integration into a broader institutional development plan. It aims to deliver new evidence on RTT autonomy and standardized training models.

Design and Method

A prospective quality improvement initiative should enhance RTT autonomy in IGRT: twenty RTTs will undergo 33 hours of theoretical and practical training under RO supervision. Competence will be assessed through pre- and post-course testing and a pilot phase where selected RTTs independently perform CBCT image matching. RO offline review will be a benchmark for concordance.

Discussion

Structured training empowers RTTs to contribute autonomously to IGRT processes, improving workflow and potentially reducing treatment times. The project identifies organisational, educational,

and cultural challenges, including the need for clear protocols, staff engagement, and interprofessional collaboration.

Conclusion

Structured training enables RTTs to perform IGRT image matching independently, within validated protocols. This intervention should reduce reliance on ROs, streamline workflow, and has potential to optimize resource allocation. Broader adoption could enhance quality and efficiency of radiotherapy delivery while fostering interprofessional collaboration.

Keywords

IGRT, Therapeutic Radiographer, Radiotherapy, Image Matching, Professional Training, Workflow Efficiency

INTRODUCTION

Hypotheses

Specific training enables Therapeutic Radiographers (RTTs) to manage the image-matching phase of IGRT independently, thereby reducing treatment time and improving organisational efficiency.

Practitioners would be able to assess whether to continue with the treatment, based on values according to validated and shared company protocols, taking into account the displacements detected during the acquisition, thus contributing to the rationalization of the processes involved in the administration phase of the radiotherapy session.

Radiotherapy (RT) is essential in treating various cancers, providing both curative and palliative benefits globally. Advances in imaging, computing, and treatment delivery have significantly enhanced RT precision, minimizing harm to surrounding healthy tissues.

Image-Guided Radiation Therapy (IGRT) exemplifies this advancement by enabling clinicians to visualize patient anatomy immediately before treatment, facilitating precise adjustments and sub-millimetric accuracy; it has demonstrated improved tumor control and reduced toxicity, especially in treatments requiring tight margins or involving mobile targets.

Modern IGRT workflows frequently utilize cone-beam CT (CBCT) matching, making matching accuracy critical to treatment quality.

Despite technological progress, image matching responsibilities often remain within the exclusive purview of Radiation Oncologists (ROs), leading to workflow inefficiencies and potential treatment delays [1].

Literature emphasizes RTTs' expanding expertise and underscores the need for continuous training and refresher courses due to rapid technological advancements.

A.S.T.R.O. Health Policy Guidelines reiterate Radiation Oncologists' (RO) supervisory responsibilities, acknowledging that trained RTTs can perform imaging evaluations and adjustments under RO oversight [2].

Similarly, ASMIRT (Australian Society of Medical Imaging and Radiation Therapy), have acknowledged the possibility for trained RTTs to independently perform specific IGRT tasks under appropriate supervision [2], and the Italian scientific society of Radiation Therapists (A.I.T.R.O.) advocate ongoing

RTT skill development through structured theoretical and practical training, adherence to specific protocols, and clearly defined autonomy limits for various treatments [3,4].

Recent multicenter studies have demonstrated that adequately trained RTTs can achieve image-matching accuracy comparable to that of physicians [5,6]. However, most published evidence to date is limited to retrospective analyses [6], anatomically specific implementations [7], or qualitative, non-standardized experiences [8], highlighting the need for structured, reproducible protocols that can be integrated into routine clinical workflows.

Aim

This project is conducted by the Professional development and implementation of research in health professions unit, (Sviluppo Professionale ed Implementazione della Ricerca per le professioni sanitarie - S.S.D. SPIR) at IRCCS Azienda Ospedaliero-Universitaria (AOU) di Bologna, Policlinico di S. Orsola; in addition, it represents a budget objective for the Direction of the Healthcare Professions of the same organisation.

The objective of this project is based on a change of vision aimed at strengthening the professional role of the RTTs in the management of the IGRT, with a consequent streamlining of the procedures for the delivery of treatment and a reduction in their timing, as well as a reduced cost for the company dictated by different levels of negotiation between Radiation Oncologists and RTTs.

In the cited document, A.I.T.R.O. intends to present a training project for RTTs that can be used to improve training, with the aim of incorporating them into IGRT and ART assessment procedures [3].

The project's training comprises theoretical lectures and practical sessions supervised by radiation oncologists, enhancing RTT autonomy in image matching and decision-making. Increased RTT competence is expected to foster collaborative multidisciplinary teamwork, optimize treatment times, and maintain high treatment quality standards. Specifically, the project aims to define essential RTT skills, establish standardized image-matching protocols, and promote continuous RTT training.

This initiative is distinguished by its multidimensional approach, encompassing clinical, educational, and organizational outcomes. It aims to provide reproducible evidence to support RTT role expansion and to contribute toward the definition of national standards for IGRT training and practice.

This study uniquely integrates structured theoretical training, assessments, a supervised pilot phase for independent image matching, and inclusion in hospital-wide professional development initiatives. This comprehensive approach assesses knowledge efficacy, practical performance, organizational impact, and potential scalability, contributing toward national standardization.

These aspects provide the fundamental basis for building a collaborative and integrated relationship within a multidisciplinary group, such as those operating in radiotherapy, rather than limiting the autonomy of RTTs: allowing RTTs to perform this activity autonomously can help optimize timing and improve treatment quality.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This protocol proposes a structured educational intervention aimed at enhancing the autonomy of RTTs in the execution of CBCT-based image matching within IGRT workflows. Its originality lies not only in the implementation of a study design in alignment with internationally recognized

methodological standards (SQUIRE 2.0), but also in its integration into the broader institutional framework for professional development and clinical innovation.

It includes objective assessments of technical competencies, and is embedded within the institutional professional development framework of the IRCCS Azienda Ospedaliero-Universitaria di Bologna, in accordance with a budget objective for the Director of Healthcare Professions, in accordance with the Article 45 of the Italian National Collective Labour Agreement for the Healthcare Sector [9].

Context

The project will be conducted within the Radiotherapy Unit of the IRCCS Azienda Ospedaliero-Universitaria di Bologna, which is equipped with three Elekta AB linear accelerators ((LINACs), including the latest systems (VERSAHDs) integrated with Surface Guided Radiation Therapy (SGRT) technology.

The project's strengths and opportunities, as well as its weaknesses and threats, are highlighted by this SWOT analysis (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 Project SWOT analysis

The SWOT analysis reveals clear **strengths** and advantages, as a rapid review of work resulting in continuous quality improvement and a structured pathway facilitating learning and implementation (which should result in simplified work). Additionally, there should be reduced risks and enhanced professional growth, as well as the opportunity to acquire new skills in a dynamic context.

One potential **weakness** could be the need for greater physician involvement in supervision: if on the one hand, this would guarantee quality, on the other hand it could initially slow down processes.

Shared evaluation criteria would also need to be implemented to address subjectivity in image review; finally, although time-consuming, investment in training is essential for improving competence and work quality.

The **opportunities** highlighted include launching a pilot project, a unique opportunity to gather feedback and refine the system, acquiring and consolidating new skills in an evolving sector, and enabling professionals to remain at the forefront of their field.

Multidisciplinary collaboration promotes innovation, and the implementation of the system opens the door to new research projects and the creation of shared guidelines — both of which are fundamental to effective, quality work.

The possibility that people may resist change is a big **threat** that needs a proactive approach. This means effective communication and staff participation. Furthermore, the absence of shared, nationally standardized documents could hinder the implementation and dissemination of the project, but could also stimulate the creation of new, nationally shared guidelines.

A Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) has been developed to support the planning and execution of activities. It describes the main deliverables and related project activities, with the involvement of the RT Centre Head and the Physics Service Head (Fig. 2).

A briefing session will be planned with the RTT team and will be attended by the Director of Healthcare Professions, the Head of Technical Services and the RTT Coordinator.

WORK BREAKDOWN STRUCTURE

Fig. 2 Work Breakdown Structure

Study design

Participants

Twenty RTTs currently employed at the center will be invited to participate, and will be divided into two groups to facilitate learning and minimize disruptions to clinical workflow. The grouping aims to optimize participant interaction and educational efficiency while maintaining uninterrupted clinical operations.

Educational intervention

The project comprises the following key implementation phases.

- Theoretical phase

Participants will undergo a comprehensive educational program consisting of both theoretical and practical components. The theoretical phase includes a series of lectures totaling 33 hours, delivered by a multidisciplinary team comprising ROs, medical physicists, and application specialists. Topics covered will encompass IGRT protocols by anatomical region (gastroenteric system, prostate, gynecological treatments, pancreas, thorax, head and neck, upper and inferior limbs), image interpretation, anatomical considerations, geometric error management, professional responsibility, Adaptive Radiotherapy (ART) principles, quality assurance protocols.

The structure of the educational intervention is based and developed on a training proposal shared by A.I.T.R.O., personalised according to the technological equipment of the specific RT centre (full programme is available in supplementary material - "Course programme_ theoretical section").

The theoretical training will be divided into 4 sessions (2 sessions for each group of professionals), covering the following topics:

- 1) *1st edition (24 hours): General part and radiotherapy of the abdominal area (1st group);*
- 2) *2nd edition (24 hours): General part and radiotherapy of the abdominal area (2nd group);*
- 3) *3rd edition (9 hours): Radiotherapy of other anatomical areas (1st group);*
- 4) *4th edition (9 hours): Radiotherapy of other anatomical areas (2nd group).*

In addition, in line with the RT centre's technological equipment, a training course will be provided to refresh the integration of SGRT technologies with radiation units, and will be structured into two specific sessions:

- 1) CT simulation of respiratory studies (DIBH and 4D/free breathing techniques);
- 2) respiratory gating techniques in the therapy room.

- Practical phase

The practical component of the educational program will provide participants with supervised, hands-on experience in image matching using Cone Beam CT (CBCT) images. Initially, RTTs will perform these tasks under direct supervision, progressively transitioning towards independent assessments as their competencies develop. Performance monitoring will involve direct observational assessments and systematic comparison of RTT-generated image-matching results with those from expert ROs.

Fig. 3 Project timeline

Evaluation methods

To objectively evaluate the effectiveness of the training intervention, participants will complete a pre-course knowledge assessment test and an identical post-course test upon completion of the theoretical phase (Supplementary material - "Multiple-choice questionnaire"):

- 1) Pre-test (multiple-choice questionnaire) with 22 questions to assess the fundamental knowledge of participants in the theoretical course at time T0.
- 2) Post-test (the same multiple-choice questionnaire) to check the degree of autonomy achieved, at time T1.

The practical effectiveness will be assessed through systematic comparisons of displacement vectors recorded by RTTs against those identified by ROs during patient image verification sessions. Additionally, supplementary metrics, including course completion rates and participant satisfaction, will be collected using structured Likert-scale questionnaires.

The professional section of the course will consist of RTTs' on-the-job training, supported by ROs. RTTs will work closely with an R.O. to meticulously review CBCT images, receiving instructions throughout the process. At the end of the process, they will be required to independently review the original images in order to identify any significant discrepancies in line with the ROs' instructions. By the end of the training, RTTs will be able to examine images independently using this approach and make a preliminary assessment of potential changes, which they will record on specific reports (Table 1).

RTT	name_surname					AUTOMATIC Matching (T)			RTT Matching (T)			RO Matching (T)			AUTOMATIC Matching (R)			RTT Matching (R)			RO Matching (R)				
Patient ID	Session	Date	LINAC	Anatomical district	technique	x	y	z	x	y	z	x	y	z	x	y	z	x	y	z	x	y	z		

Table 1: Report of matches detected through co-registration, with corrections applied by RTTs and ROs.

Regarding the specific approach to matching during normal activities, it would be most appropriate to begin the professional section with a **pilot group of five RTTs**, to minimise the impact on clinical workflow.

The method adopted to measure the different approaches to matching activities will involve verifying and comparing geometric deviations detected by the RTTs and R.O. (Supplementary material - Report Matching Online).

An additional control phase will be conducted in the period following the training, during which the RTTs, who are part of the pilot group, will independently carry out the online Cone Beam CT image matching verification phase during patient treatment.

This will be double-checked offline by ROs to identify any significant discrepancies between the planning CT images and the Cone Beam CT images: an in-depth evaluation will then be carried out to determine the success and effectiveness of the training.

Endpoints

The primary endpoints include:

- availability of institutional procedures, in accordance with specific quality requirements and radiotherapy centre's organisational standards (structural indicator)
- improvement in theoretical knowledge, as measured by a validated 22-item multiple-choice questionnaire completed before and after the course;
- specific level of agreement between RTTs and radiation oncologists in identifying displacement vectors during IGRT image matching.

The agreement is represented by the proportion of concordant matches per RTT. For each CBCT registration, a match is considered concordant if the absolute difference between the RTT- and RO-recorded corrections is:

- ❖ ≤ 1 mm in all translational axes (LR, SI, AP) and $\leq 1^\circ$ in each rotational axis (pitch, roll, yaw) for treatments delivered with hypofractionated or stereotactic body radiotherapy (SBRT; ≤ 5 fractions);
- ❖ ≤ 2 mm and $\leq 2^\circ$ for conventionally fractionated VMAT/IMRT courses (> 5 fractions).

Additional secondary endpoints comprise:

- ❖ number of participants and sessions completed (process indicators);
- ❖ participant-reported satisfaction levels and perceptions of training effectiveness, evaluated through Likert-scale surveys (Supplementary material - Training satisfaction survey).

Furthermore, the study will evaluate the proportion of independently performed image reviews deemed acceptable by retrospective evaluation conducted by ROs.

Expected Results

Protocol success will be declared if the median concordance across RTTs is $\geq 90\%$ and the lower bound of the 95% confidence interval (CI) is $\geq 85\%$ for both fractionation classes. Agreement will be further quantified using the intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC, two-way random, absolute agreement) for each translational axis; values ≥ 0.90 will be interpreted as excellent reliability. Bland–Altman plots will be produced as supportive analyses to visualize systematic offsets.

DISCUSSION

The originality of this project lies not only in the implementation of a structured design rooted in internationally endorsed methodological standards (SQUIRE 2.0), applied as quality improvement guidance rather than clinical trial protocol, but also in its integration into the broader institutional framework for professional development and clinical innovation, combining didactic instruction, supervised clinical practice, and objective evaluation metrics in a real-world clinical setting.

This positions the initiative as a potentially transformative model, bridging the gap between experimental feasibility and organizational applicability.

The inclusion of this initiative as a formally budgeted institutional goal not only legitimizes RTT role expansion but also reinforces the value of interdisciplinary collaboration in radiotherapy services.

Additionally, the choice to include a general RTT population, rather than pre-selected or highly specialized personnel, increases the generalizability and real-world relevance of the findings. Several strengths distinguish this initiative: its methodological rigor, modular and multidisciplinary educational design, and structured outcome evaluation plan. The use of concordance metrics (e.g., intraclass correlation, Bland–Altman plots) offers robust insight into performance reliability, while Likert-scale surveys and knowledge assessments enrich the analysis with qualitative and quantitative feedback.

It would be better if the training was finalised in the initial phase for hyperfractionated radiotherapy treatments for adult patients, in order to conduct a more detailed study of stereotactic and/or paediatric treatments in a later phase.

Nonetheless, limitations must be acknowledged. Cultural resistance to role redefinition, differences in infrastructure across centers, and variable acceptance by medical staff may also influence implementation outcomes. Future directions should prioritize multi-center implementation, long term

tracking of performance indicators, and inclusion of patient-related outcomes to assess safety, satisfaction, and perceived quality of care. The creation of a national training framework or accreditation pathway could facilitate standardized skill acquisition and foster professional recognition of RTTs in advanced IGRT roles.

Limitations on the generalisability of the project should be also potential limits to internal validity, such as confounding factors, bias, or inadequacies in the design, methods, indicators or analysis.

Any discrepancies between the observed and anticipated outcomes could be attributable to contextual factors, such as organisational challenges in executing the training programme, or opposition from the personnel involved.

All necessary strategies will be employed to ensure that the professionals involved have transparent access to the training programmes and are aware of the project's impact on care.

A comprehensive study should not include professionals who are due to be transferred or assigned to a different department or company, as they will automatically be excluded from observation once the study has begun.

Participants who did not attend the course (either partially or completely) will be recorded as missing data. This will provide a comprehensive overview of the intervention's efficacy.

The analysis of pre and post-test scores should focus on a hypothetical assessment of the effectiveness of the training.

Furthermore, correlation analysis (Spearman or Pearson) may reveal any correlation between satisfaction and performance by comparing satisfaction and post-test scores.

This project contributes meaningfully to the ongoing discourse on radiotherapy workforce development, offering not only clinical and operational insights, but also strategic direction for healthcare policy, education, and practice.

CONCLUSIONS

In order to define the complete value of the project, the study's findings on the complexity of the entire project are highlighted, with the integration of efforts at multiple levels of responsibility and professionalism being emphasised, starting with organisational and management planning, through technical coordination, to the modification of practices currently in use in the Operational Unit (OU) (from organizational and managerial planning, through technical coordination, to the adaptation of daily practices within the OU), with the ultimate goal of improving performance.

To evaluate critical issues related to the project's development and orient future analogue research, we could ensure the availability of ROs for training purposes and implement shared protocols for anatomical districts (ensuring the structured involvement of Radiation Oncologists (ROs) for training purposes, together with the implementation of shared protocols across different anatomical districts, will be essential).

In terms of sustainability, the focus should be on the benefits of assigning this role to RTTs, particularly with regard to process rationalisation and reduced treatment times. Embedding the project within the institutional framework for professional development, in accordance with Article 45 of the Italian

National Collective Labour Agreement (CCNL), and in line with the objectives of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR), further reinforces its feasibility and long-term applicability.

Currently, only a small percentage of Italian centres provide RTTs with a structured training course that enables them to independently perform image verification activities in radiotherapy. In most cases, this activity is taught on the job as an additional task.

This training project could be an interesting pilot study with great potential for dissemination to other contexts, and it could be replicated in other centres that intend to transfer this activity to RTTs. This exploratory institutional initiative demonstrates a replicable model that may be disseminated to other centers wishing to expand RTT roles in IGRT, aligning with international recommendations (e.g. ASTRO, ESTRO, ASMIRT) and contributing to the definition of a potential national training framework.

Acknowledgments

The work reported in this publication was funded by the Italian Ministry of Health, RC-2025-2795987.

REFERENCES

1. Forde E, Josipovic M, Kamphuis M, Lopez J, Remeijer P, Rivera S, et al. What does “Advanced” mean in 2023? Reflecting on 10 years of the ESTRO Advanced Skills in Modern Radiotherapy course. *Tech Innov Patient Support Radiat Oncol.* 2024;29:100227. doi:10.1016/j.tipsro.2023.100227.
2. American Society for Radiation Oncology (ASTRO). *Health policy coding guidance: Image guided radiation therapy coding and physician supervision guidelines.* 2013
3. Australian Society of Medical Imaging and Radiation Therapy (ASMIRT), Pathway to Advanced Practice. 2017. <https://asmirt.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/129.pdf>
4. Associazione Italiana Tecnici di Radioterapia Oncologica e Fisica Sanitaria (AITRO). *Indicazioni all'utilizzo dei sistemi di radioterapia a guida di immagine: Position paper.* 2019
5. Kim B, Kirkby C, Semaka A, Debenham B, Campbell T. Assessment of IGRT variability for lung SBRT. *J Med Imaging Radiat Sci.* 2021 Jun;52(2):191–7. doi:10.1016/j.jmir.2021.02.004.
6. Levin D, Grinfeld G, Greenberg V, Lipsky Y, Zalmanov-Fayerman S, Tova Y, et al. Real-time online matching in high dose-per-fraction treatments: do radiation therapists perform as well as physicians? *Pract Radiat Oncol.* 2019 Mar;9(2):e236–e241. doi:10.1016/j.ppro.2018.10.002.
7. Alexander SE, Hopkins N, Lalondrelle S, Taylor A, Titmarsh K, McNair HA. RTT-led IGRT for cervix cancer: training, implementation and validation. *Tech Innov Patient Support Radiat Oncol.* 2019;12:41–9. doi:10.1016/j.tipsro.2019.10.007.
8. Sousa F, Somoano M, Jourani Y, Van Gestel D. Qualitative evaluation of the role of RTTs IGRT specialists and their influence on treatment delivery. *Tech Innov Patient Support Radiat Oncol.* 2022;22:9-15. doi:10.1016/j.tipsro.2022.03.002
9. Italian Government. *National collective labour agreement for the healthcare sector 2019–2021. Art. 45.* Rome: ARAN; 2022